

MITIGATING SOIL MOISTURE DEFICIT STRESS IN RAINFED CHICKPEA (*Cicer arietinum* L.) THROUGH HYDROGEL AND PLANT GROWTH REGULATORS

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Abstract

In order to find out the effect of hydrogel application and foliar nutrients spray on chickpea an experiment entitled "Mitigating soil moisture deficit stress in rainfed chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) through hydrogel and plant growth regulators" was conducted during rabi season of 2022-23. The experiment was conducted at Agricultural Research Station, Badnapur, Dist. Jalna under jurisdiction of VNMKV university, Parbhani (MS). The treatments comprised of three levels of hydrogel application (0, 2.5 and 5 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel, respectively) and six levels of plant growth regulators foliar application viz. (F₁- water spray, F₂- urea 2%, F₃- thiourea 500 ppm, F₄- salicylic acid 100 ppm, F₅- NPK (19:19:19) 0.5% and F₆- DAP 2%). The experiment was laid out in split plot design with four replications having hydrogel application as main plot and foliar application of plant growth regulators as sub plot treatment. The region has semi-arid climate. The chickpea variety BDNG-797 was sown on November 4th, 2022 and harvested on March 15th, 2023. The seed rate of 65 kg ha⁻¹ treated with rhizobium culture was used for the sowing. A basal application of 25:50:00 kg ha⁻¹ N: P₂O₅: K₂O was given to the crop through soil. One irrigation was applied just after sowing of the crop. The hydrogel as per treatment was drilled in line before seeding of chickpea seeds. The plant growth regulators were applied as per treatment at flower initiation stage (45 DAS) and pod development stage (70 DAS). Among hydrogel application treatments, application of 5 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel produced the highest seed (2105 kg ha⁻¹) and stover yield (2899 kg ha⁻¹). The maximum seed yield was recorded with foliar application of F₅- NPK (19: 19: 19) 0.5 %, which was comparable with the foliar application of F₃- thiourea 500 ppm and F₄- salicylic acid for seed and stover yield.

Keywords: Hydrogel, foliar, spray, nutrients, chickpea, *Cicer arietinum* L.

Introduction

Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) is an important winter season pulse crop. It is a rich source of protein and plays an important role in human nutrition for large population in the developing world. Pulses contain a high percentage of quality protein nearly three times as much as cereal. Chickpea is valued for its nutritive seeds with high protein content (18-22%), carbohydrate (52-70%), fat (4-10%), minerals, calcium (Ca), phosphorus (P), iron (Fe) and vitamins. However, chickpea is a high protein yielding grain legume besides groundnut and soybean. One hundred grams of chickpea seeds provides 360 calories of energy. Generally, chickpea is grown on residual soil moisture as rainfed crop and its high nutritional value makes chickpea an important food particularly in drought prone areas of the world. Chickpea can fix up to 140 kg N ha⁻¹ in a growing period (Poonia and Pithia, 2013) [9] and gives substantial amount of residual nitrogen for subsequent crops and adds plenty of organic matter through leaves and roots to maintain and improve soil health and fertility.

India is one of the most important chickpea growing country in Asia with an area of 9698.75 thousand ha with the production of 11078.50 thousand tonnes and average productivity of 1142 kg ha⁻¹. Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka are the major chickpea producing states, respectively sharing over 95% area. Chickpea is an important winter season pulse crop and stands first among the rabi pulses in Maharashtra. Chickpea is grown over an area of 23.72 lakh ha. with an annual production of 27.15 lakh tonnes and an average productivity of 1145 kg ha⁻¹ in Maharashtra (Anonymous, 2021-22) [1].

Chickpea is mainly cultivated with traditional methods under arid and semi-arid regions where shortage of water during crop growth period has become the major impediments for its cultivation. The stress crunch of inefficient use of rain and irrigation water by rainfed crops is the most important problem in semiarid and arid regions. Rainfed agriculture has a protruding role to play in India's agriculture and economy. Rainfed areas are home to the majority of rural poor and marginal farmers, who come across multiple risk and uncertainties relating to bio-physical and socio-economic conditions

resulting in poverty, malnutrition, water scarcity, severe land degradation, lower yields, low investments, and poor physical and social infrastructure. Under dryland/rainfed condition, application of water saving super absorbent polymers (SAP) i.e. hydrogel into the soil could be an effective way to increase both water and nutrient use efficiency in crops (Lentz *et al.*, 1998) [6]. Hydrogel is generally drilled in the soil before sowing of the crop, it is presumed that hydrogel retain large quantities of water and nutrients, which are released as and when required by plant and thus plant growth could be improved under limited water and nutrient supply (Gehring and Lewis, 1980) [3]. The super absorbent polymer (hydrogel) potentially influenced soil permeability, density, structure, texture, evaporation and infiltration rates of water through the soils. Particularly, the hydrogels reduce irrigation frequency and compaction tendency, stops erosion, water runoff and increase the soil aeration and microbial activity (Halagalimath and Rajkumara, 2017) [5].

Foliar application of nutrients has been proved to be an important asset of fertilizer application with the specific aim of increasing nutrient availability at the time of need. Though the emphasis has been laid down for foliar fertilization of trace elements yet it has repeatedly been observed that the foliar application of macronutrients too, had a positive impact on plant metabolism and ultimately on yields. The nitrogen supply can be maintained through foliar application at lower concentration by the bioregulators that act as chemical catalyst in plants and improves physiological and reproductive efficiency in the plant. These bioregulators possibly improve the gene expression for efficient sucrose transport and increases dry matter partitioning for grain production (Werdan *et al.*, 1975) [11]. Nutrient management (major and minor) is the main component for sustainable chickpea production along with foliar application of watersoluble fertilizer at appropriate stages of growth may also ameliorate the nutrient deficiency as well as mitigate the heat stress. Foliar application of urea has been found effective in increasing the nitrogen availability to developing seeds in pulses (Palta *et al.*, 2005) [8], whereas thiourea, a sulphhydryl compound plays a significant role in improving dry matter distribution for seed yield (Ghanshyam, 2000) [4]. Thiourea helps in better translocation of photosynthates from source to sink and also reduces the nitrate reductase activity. It contains 42% sulphur and

36% nitrogen and has been used so far chiefly for breaking dormancy and stimulating germination of seeds.

Materials and Methods

The experiment "Mitigating soil moisture deficit stress in rainfed chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) through hydrogel and plant growth regulators" was conducted at Agricultural Research Station, Badnapur, under jurisdiction of university, VNMKV, Parbhani (MS), during rabi season of 2022-23. The treatments comprised of three levels of hydrogel application (0 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel; 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel and 5 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel) and six levels of plant growth regulators foliar application (F₁- water spray, F₂- urea 2%, F₃- thiourea 500 ppm, F₄- salicylic acid 100 ppm, F₅- NPK (19:19:19) 0.5% and F₆- DAP 2%). The experiment was laid out in split plot design with four replications having hydrogel application as main plot and foliar application of plant growth regulators as sub plot treatment. The climate of the region is semi-arid. The soil of experimental plot was clay loam, slightly alkaline in reaction (pH 8.14) having an organic carbon content of 0.58% and low amount of available nitrogen (137.86 kg ha⁻¹), medium phosphorus (19.77 kg ha⁻¹) and high potassium (405.82 kg ha⁻¹) content. Chickpea variety BDNG-797 was sown on November 4th, 2022 and harvested on March 15th, 2023. During crop growth period various growth and yield attributing characters like plant height, number of branches pods plant⁻¹, seeds pod⁻¹, 100 seeds weight, seed yield and stover yield were taken as per schedule and requirement of investigation.

Results and Discussion

Growth and yield attributes of chickpea

Table 9: Growth and yield attributes of chickpea as influenced by hydrogel application and plant growth regulator

Treatments	Plant height (cm)	Number of branches plant ⁻¹	Number of pods plant ⁻¹	Seed index
Main plot: Hydrogel application before sowing				
T ₁ : 0	42.38	5.6	46.67	22.22
T ₂ : 2.5 kg ha ⁻¹	44.09	6.5	50.58	22.94
T ₃ : 5.0 kg ha ⁻¹	45.13	7.1	55.00	23.05
SE ±	0.58	0.16	0.87	0.11
CD at 5 %	2.04	0.57	3.06	0.38
Sub plot: Plant growth regulator				
F ₁ : Water spray (control)	40.89	5.4	46.75	22.89
F ₂ : Urea 2%	43.20	6.0	49.83	22.67
F ₃ : Thiourea 500 ppm	44.74	7.3	54.00	22.44
F ₄ : Salicylic acid 100 ppm	44.85	6.6	52.83	22.67
F ₅ : NPK (19:19:19) 0.5%	45.98	7.6	57.00	23.11
F ₆ : GA 3 @ 30 ppm	43.53	5.6	44.08	22.66
SE ±	0.56	0.34	1.39	0.23
CD at 5 %	1.61	0.96	3.96	NS
Interactions (T x F)				
SE ±	1.06	0.82	3.39	0.11
CD at 5 %	NS	NS	NS	NS
C.V. (%)	8.63	12.25	10.74	3.58
General Mean	43.4	6.4	50.5	22.7

Seed yield (kg ha⁻¹)

The data presented in Table 2 revealed that the application of hydrogel and plant growth regulators treatments influenced significantly seed yield of chickpea. Hydrogel application @ 5.0 kg ha⁻¹ recorded significantly higher seed yield (2105 Kg ha⁻¹) than no hydrogel application level but found at par with hydrogel application @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹. The lowest seed yield was obtained by control. The increase in seed yield due to hydrogel application in different crops have been also reported by Boatright *et al.* (1997) and Shankarappa *et al.* (2020) [2, 10]. Among the plant growth regulators, significantly higher seed yield was recorded by the treatment NPK (19:19:19) 0.5% (F₅) (2108 Kg ha⁻¹) which was found at par with treatment Thiourea 500 ppm application (F₃) and Salicylic acid 100 ppm (F₄). While the lowest seed yield was recorded by control (water spray).

Hydrogel application @ 5.0 kg ha⁻¹ (T₃) recorded significantly higher plant height than no hydrogel application treatment and was found to be at par with the treatment hydrogel application @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ (T₂). Similar trend was found in case of number of branches plant⁻¹, number of pods plant⁻¹ and seed index. Similar results have been also reported by Boatright *et al.* (1997) and Shankarappa *et al.* (2020) [2, 10].

This variation in the seed index might be due to seed size and seed diameter which is genetic character of chickpea. Similar results have been also reported by Boatright *et al.* (1997) [2]. Among plant growth regulators, the treatment foliar application of NPK (19:19:19) 0.5% (F₅) recorded highest value of plant height and number of branches plant⁻¹ which was found to be at par with the treatment foliar application of salicylic acid 100 ppm (F₄) and foliar application of Thiourea 500 ppm (F₃) and significantly superior over rest of the treatments. Whereas, highest number of pods plant⁻¹ were recorded by the treatment foliar application of NPK (19:19:19) 0.5% (F₅) which was found to be significantly superior over rest of the treatments except foliar application of Thiourea 500 ppm treatment (F₃). This might be due to foliar application of NPK (19:19:19) which increases the translocation of assimilates to sink. Similar results have been also reported by Palta *et al.* (2005) [8]. Seed index was not influenced significantly by the application of various plant growth regulators.

Interaction effect hydrogel application and plant growth regulator (T x F) was found to be non-significant for all growth and yield attributes of chickpea.

This might be due to the fact that foliar spray of nutrients increases the photosynthetic activities of plants, which in turn increase the active leaf surface during the grain filling period, facilitating the best partitioning of the source and sink and creating the congenial atmosphere in plants for enhancing the yield. Foliar spraying of NPK (19:19:19) might have retarded the loss of chlorophyll and leaf nitrogen with increased photosynthetic ability resulting in enhanced seed yield. Similar observation was also reported by Mitra *et al.* (1987) [7]. While the interaction between hydrogel application and plant growth regulators was found to be non-significant.

Stover yield (kg ha⁻¹)

Highest value of stover yield was recorded by the treatment hydrogel application @ 5.0 kg ha⁻¹ (T₃) (2899 Kg ha⁻¹) which was significantly superior over no hydrogel application level but found to be at par with

hydrogel application @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹. Similar results have been also reported by Boatright et al. (1997) and Shankarappa et al. (2020) ^{12, 101}. In case of plant growth regulators, application of NPK (19:19:19) 0.5% recorded highest value of stover yield (2908 Kg ha⁻¹) which was on par with treatment Thiourea 500 ppm (F₃), Salicylic acid 100 ppm (F₄) and GA 3 @ 30 ppm (F₆) and significantly superior over rest of the treatments. Whereas, the interaction between hydrogel application and plant growth regulators was found to be non-

significant.

Harvest index (%)

Numerically highest value of harvest index was recorded by the treatment hydrogel application @ 5.0 kg ha⁻¹ (T₃) (41.91%) and the treatment application of NPK (19:19:19) 0.5% (F₅) (41.84%) with general mean of 41.10 %. This might be due to higher accumulation of photosynthates and translocation of nutrients to economic part of the crop.

Table 2: Seed Yield (Kg ha⁻¹), Stover Yield (Kg ha⁻¹) and Harvest Index (%) of chickpea as influenced by hydrogel application and plant growth regulators

Treatments	Seed Yield (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Stover Yield (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Harvest Index (%)
Main plot: Hydrogel application before sowing			
T ₁ : 0	1737	2611	39.90
T ₂ : 2.5 kg ha ⁻¹	1967	2776	41.33
T ₃ : 5.0 kg ha ⁻¹	2105	2899	41.91
SE ±	39.90	37.80	-
CD at 5 %	140.77	133.35	-
Sub plot: Plant growth regulator			
F ₁ : Water spray (control)	1652	2508	39.66
F ₂ : Urea 2%	1895	2737	40.80
F ₃ : Thiourea 500 ppm	2042	2865	41.49
F ₄ : Salicylic acid 100 ppm	1979	2791	41.32
F ₅ : NPK (19:19:19) 0.5%	2108	2908	41.84
F ₆ : GA 3 @ 30 ppm	1940	2765	41.19
SE ±	57.84	54.47	-
CD at 5 %	165.30	155.65	-
Interactions (T x F)			
SE ±	99.78	94.05	-
CD at 5 %	NS	NS	-
C.V. (%)	10.12	6.83	-
General Mean	1936	2762	41.10

Gross monetary return (Rs. ha⁻¹)

The highest GMR was observed with hydrogel application @ 5.0 kg ha⁻¹ which was found to be at par with hydrogel application @ 2.5 kg ha⁻¹ and significantly superior over no hydrogel application treatment. The lowest GMR was obtained by control. Among the plant growth regulators, significantly higher GMR was recorded by NPK (19:19:19) 0.5% (F₅) which was found at par with treatment Thiourea 500 ppm (F₃) and Salicylic acid 100 ppm (F₄) and found to be significantly superior over rest of the treatments. Whereas, the interaction between hydrogel application and plant growth regulators was found to be non-significant.

Net monetary return (Rs. ha⁻¹)

The treatment hydrogel application @ 5.0 kg ha⁻¹ (T₃) recorded significantly higher NMR (63376 Rs. ha⁻¹) than rest of the treatments.

The lowest value of NMR was recorded by control. Among plant growth regulators, application of NPK (19:19:19) 0.5% recorded highest value of NMR (64323 Rs. ha⁻¹) which was on par with treatment Thiourea 500 ppm (F₃), Salicylic acid 100 ppm (F₄) and GA 3 @ 30 ppm (F₆) and significantly superior over rest of the treatments. Whereas, the interaction effect between hydrogel application and plant growth regulators was found to be non-significant.

B:C ratio

Numerically, higher value of B:C ratio was recorded by the treatment hydrogel application @ 5.0 kg ha⁻¹ (T₃) followed by no hydrogel application. Among the plant growth regulators, higher value of B:C ratio was recorded by NPK (19:19:19) 0.5% (F₅) followed by the treatment Salicylic acid (F₄) and GA 3 @ 30 ppm (F₆).

Table 3: Economics of chickpea as influenced by hydrogel application and plant growth regulators

Treatments	Seed Yield (Kg ha ⁻¹)	GMR (Rs ha ⁻¹)	NMR (Rs ha ⁻¹)	B:C ratio
Main plot: Hydrogel application before sowing				
T ₁ : 0	1737	86182	51299	2.47
T ₂ : 2.5 kg ha ⁻¹	1967	97257	55003	2.30
T ₃ : 5.0 kg ha ⁻¹	2105	103913	63376	2.56
SE ±	39.90	1932.45	1932.45	-
CD at 5 %	140.77	6817.14	6817.14	-
Sub plot: Plant growth regulator				
F ₁ : Water spray (control)	1652	82028	44542	2.19
F ₂ : Urea 2%	1895	93836	55426	2.44
F ₃ : Thiourea 500 ppm	2042	100940	58762	2.41
F ₄ : Salicylic acid 100 ppm	1979	97856	59144	2.53
F ₅ : NPK (19:19:19) 0.5%	2108	104070	64323	2.62
F ₆ : GA 3 @ 30 ppm	1940	95974	57159	2.48

	SE \pm	57.84	2802.50	2802.50	-
	CD at 5 %	165.30	8008.84	8008.84	-
Interactions (T x F)					
	SE \pm	99.78	4834.18	4834.18	-
	CD at 5 %	NS	NS	NS	-
	C.V. (%)	10.12	10.12	16.80	-
	General Mean	1936	95784	56559	2.44

Conclusion

The application of 5 kg ha⁻¹ hydrogel produced the highest seed yield, stover yield, GMR and NMR as compared to without application of hydrogel under limited irrigation supply. The foliar nutrient spray of NPK (19:19:19) 0.5% at flower initiation and pod development stages, enhanced seed yield, stover yield, GMR and NMR which was comparable with the foliar nutrient spray of Thiourea 500 ppm Salicylic acid 100 ppm.

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